

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Report on Cycle 1 hackathon
Deliverable number	D44 (Del. Rel. No. D8.5)
Revision	0
Status	Final
Planned delivery date	30/04/2022
Actual date of issue	23/04/2022
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	WU
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

This document is a report on the Cycle 1 hackathon, which was designed to make the NextGEMS PIs familiar with the data produced by storm-resolving models.

Work package in charge:

WP8

Lead author:

Chiel van Heerwaarden

Other contributing authors:

Imme Benedict

Internal reviewer(s):

1st reviewer: Cathy Hohenegger

2nd reviewer: Theresa Mieslinger

Contacts: chiel.vanheerwaarden@wur.nl

Visit us on: www.nextgems-h2020.eu

Disclaimer: This material reflects only the authors view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

1 Executive summary	4
2 Conclusion & Results	4
3 Project objectives	4
4 Detailed report on the deliverable	7
4.1 Photo and video documentation	7
4.2 Statistics	9
4.3 Data handling	10
4.4 Knowledge Coproduction component on Solar Energy	10
4.5 First model evaluation	10
5 References (Bibliography)	11
6 Dissemination and uptake	11
6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience	11
6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience	11
7 Deliverable timeliness	11
8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	11
9 Sustainability	12
9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects	12
10 Full track of dissemination activities	12
11 Full track of publications and IP	12

1 Executive summary

The first nextGEMS Hackathon was organized in collaboration with Storm&Society in month M4. The Knowledge Coproduction component of the Hackathon focused on selecting sites for high-frequency data logging (Task 8.3) and diagnostics (Task 8.4). The event brought for the first time the PIs together to make them acquainted with the data and to learn the tools that the PhDs and postdocs in the new positions will use. The activities helped in finding out which output data is still missing for addressing the nextGEMS research goals and deliverables. This report will describe the most important results of the first hackathon and presents its main conclusions and recommendations for the future work in the nextGEMS project.

2 Conclusion & Results

The hackathon has been a successful event for the PIs of the project to not only get to know each other but also to learn the tools and methods to access the large data sets of the ICON and IFS simulations. It has shown the great potential of global simulations at storm resolving resolution, but also the challenges of handling its very large amount of data. In addition, it has provided hints on where the models need improvement and which output variables need to be added to the current set.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Evaluate surface energy, water and momentum balance components as well as near-surface meteorology over land at storm-resolving resolution against observations and coarser resolution simulations (O1)	yes
Represent land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolution by making use of the latest generation remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation (O1)	no
Prepare the NextGEMS models to best serve the science and applications, by implementing online output statistics co-developed with stakeholders, with a pilot project focusing on solar energy (O1 and O3)	yes
Expand scope of the SR-ESM by coupling it offline to a terrestrial biosphere model (O1)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Hackathons are communal exploration, analysis and development activities – all various forms of ‘hacking’. They prioritize working together over lecturing one another. At nextGEMS meetings, our fingers do the talking. The aim of this report is the description of the first of such project meetings, the Cycle 1 Hackathon. It took place only seven weeks after the project kick-off from 19th to 22nd of October 2021. In total, 81 people from 24 institutions across Europe defied the pandemic and traveled to Berlin to meet in the Harnack Haus for 3 days of intense coding and discussions (see Fig. 1 for a group photo). A Hybrid format enabled another 15 people to participate virtually by listening to talks, engaging in open discussions, as well as through individual video calls in smaller groups.

For this first hackathon, it was anticipated to especially gather the principal investigators (PIs) to help familiarise them with the workflow, contribute to team building, and increase PI identification with the project. In total, 82.4 % of all project PIs participated, 20.6 % thereof online. Further statistics are summarized in section 4.2.

In the following, we illustrate the different aspects of the Hackathon through Photos and in a Video that gives a feeling for the atmosphere on site. Photos with impressions of the activities are found in Fig. 2.

4.1 Photo and video documentation

1. Opening discussion, introduction of the four themes and their general work and ideas for the Hackathon

At the start of the Hackathon the project was introduced by the two project PIs Bjorn Stevens and Irina Sandu. They were introducing the idea behind the project, the goal, and the context among other large-scale initiatives in earth system modelling. Furthermore, the theme leads presented their goals in the project, and the first steps to focus on during the hackathon.

2. Introduction of models, model output and data access (training component)

On Wednesday morning the models were introduced by the two modelling centres. Information was given on the physics behind the models, the coupling between the different components (ocean, land, sea ice), their resolution etc. Besides, practical information was provided on where to find the data and how to access it. A short course on software version control system Git was provided as well, to stimulate participants to share code.

3. Group work / hacking

During the hackathon the group was divided between the three themes Storms & Land, Storms & Ocean and Storms & Radiation. Within those themes small subgroups were created based on pre-defined topics. There was for example a group focused on the surface radiation balance, a group on initialization of the land, tropical circulation and stratification etc. Participants were asked to indicate their preference for the subgroups. There were two full days for the hacking. During the first day the subgroups mostly focused on finding where the data was located, in which format, and which data was available. There was technical support from DKRZ and the modelling centers. During the second day, more

progress was made in analysing the different fields, comparing data between the ICON and IFS model and observations, and finding inconsistencies in the models. On day two, subgroups of the themes also gathered to exchange information between the subgroups and to compose the final presentation for the closing discussion.

4. Networking component: not only during group work, but in coffee breaks and through social activities.

The first hackathon gave also the opportunity to get to know the group involved in the nextGEMS project. This happened during the coffee breaks, dinners, and the social activities organised during the evenings (speed date and games). For many this was the first physical event after working from home for a long time, and you could notice that people very much enjoyed to interact after a long period of only online meetings.

5. Science communication: video recordings from theme leads

During the hackathon videos of theme leads describing the science have been recorded. These videos will serve as an effective method of communicating the goals, challenges and ambitions of nextGEMS. They are part of the nextGEMS communication and dissemination strategy in form of a video blog (Vlog) and are available on the [nextGEMS website](#).

6. Closing discussion with results and collecting tasks for the model development towards Cycle 2 runs

In the closing discussion the results of the two days of hacking were shared per theme. Here, comparisons of models and observations were shown, comparison between model resolutions, as well as first insights into the weather phenomena present in the Cycle 1 simulations. Besides, a wish list was created of output variables and time frequencies for future model output.

Furthermore, the Hackathon was documented by our project partner Latest Thinking. A professional video provides a feeling for the atmosphere, people involved and the actual work performed at the hackathon and is available on our website at <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/cycle-1-hackathon>.

Figure 1: Group photo of all participants in-person and online.

Figure 2: Photo documentation of the Cycle 1 Hackathon in Berlin, Germany. Main components visible in the photos are the group work, e.g. people hacking together in groups on similar topics, plenary discussion, and interactions during coffee breaks. On top, we recorded seven overview videos describing the project and its research themes as part of our communication strategy followed by WP10

4.2 Statistics

We include basic statistics to monitor the gender and training potential of the Hackathons in Figure 3.

In meetings, especially the hackathons, we keep an eye on equal representation of all genders. Whenever there is a choice based on the scientific background, we give preference to traditionally under-represented genders as well as early career scientists for holding presentations or leading a working group. In our first hackathon in October 2021 we had an almost equal share of male (53 %) and female speakers (47 %) in the main talks¹. Only within the result presentations the share had a skewness towards male speakers which was instead in line with the ratio of all hackathon participants being female: 34 %, male: 62 %, and diverse: 3 %.

The statistics for *age* and *position* in Figure 3 reflect a large amount early- to mid-career stage participants between 30-39. As the hackathon took place very early in the project, hiring processes were still ongoing. However, fall 2021 was also a time between Covid-lockdowns that provided the chance for many scientists to meet again in person after 1.5 years of virtual meetings. Thus, several PIs send PhDs and PostDocs from their working groups to join the hackathon meeting. Many of the PhDs and PostDocs stay connected with the project, use the model output in their studies and co-develop new data workflows together with project scientists.

¹here, gender is based on people's names. All other figures and numbers relate to actual survey results.

Figure 3: Gender, age, and career stage statistics for participants of the nextGEMS Cycle 1 Hackathon.

4.3 Data handling

In preparation to the hackathon information on data handling was collected in an online book. It contains information on the model runs from IFS and ICON and visualizes the data workflow in executable scripts. Those scripts are first examples that shall make people familiar with the simulation output and facilitate the efficient analysis of such large datasets. The online book is a growing and collaborative effort available at <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/> and will be further described in the upcoming deliverable D2.1.

4.4 Knowledge Coproduction component on Solar Energy

One of the challenges of storm-resolving models is to collect meaningful statistics for users from the renewable energy sector and fisheries. In this hackathon, we started to exchange knowledge with the energy company IBERDROLA. In particular, we were discussing suitable output variables that need to be logged to make our model runs most applicable for the solar energy community. We have selected a set of solar and wind farms locations in Mexico, Brazil, Spain, and the UK with measurement stations that can be used to evaluate model output produced in the Cycle 2 runs. Furthermore, we have composed a set of variables that allow comparison of model output data to IBERDROLA's observational data. This set consists of direct and diffuse irradiance next to the common global irradiance (including clear sky components), and wind speed at wind turbine hub height. Further details on the high-frequency logging in Cycle 2 simulations at measurement stations are provided in the deliverable D8.3.

4.5 First model evaluation

One of the goals of the hackathons is to work towards well-tested and reliable models for the *production runs* in which 30-year simulations will be performed. The participants of the hackathon have performed many checks and consistency tests on the data produced by the ICON and IFS model in the first cycle. Several important issues were revealed and need addressing before the Cycle 2 data will be produced. The most important issues were i) a non-closing water and energy budget in the IFS model (fixed at the moment of writing), ii) a intertropical convergence zone (ITCZ) stuck at the equator with a too warm sea surface temperature and a decoupling of the mixed layer of the ocean (fixed at the moment of writing). iii) an energy leak in the atmosphere in the ICON model (partly fixed, ongoing work).

5 References (Bibliography)

Not applicable.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The detailed description of this hackathon could benefit organizers of similar events. The format in which new project participants work together has proven to be successful in building a consortium. This document will be freely available to the general public from the project website and linked to subsequent Hackathon advertisements to motivate young scientists and people from stakeholder groups to engage with the project. To communicate the actual outcome of the hackathon, the nextGEMS 2022 calendar has been created with the best visualizations made from data from Storm Resolving Models.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable contributes to O1 by organizing the hackathon and to O3 under A4 and A5 by setting up the collaboration with the solar power community. The report on Cycle 1 hackathon is linked to WP2 and the deliverable D2.1 describing the data workflow and to WP8 and the deliverable D8.3 on high-frequency logging. It further includes some aspects of the gender and training strategy described in D1.2.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 hackathon 19.10. – 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.4. - 3.4.2022 near Madrid

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.